

Investigation on the Adsorptive Property of Silica Gel. Part IV. Liberation of Air from Silica Gel Capillaries during Adsorption of Liquid.

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When activated silica gel adsorbs liquids, the air present in the gel capillaries is liberated. The volume relations between air displaced and the liquid adsorbed are of interest, and have been measured using a slight modification of the apparatus employed in the displacement experiment described in a previous part (p. 331).

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the apparatus shown in Fig. 1 the volume enclosed by the stop-cocks S_1 , S_2 and S_3 was carefully filled with water so that no air-bubbles were present (S_2 was kept open). The bulb A, was freed from moisture by evacuation. Activated silica gel (about 4.5 g.) was weighed and introduced into the bulb. The capillary tube C, with the mercury manometer was attached at G, and the apparatus placed in a thermostat at $30^\circ \pm 0.01$. After the attainment of the temperature of the thermostat, the manometer was read by a travelling microscope. When the pressure in the system was noticed to be constant, stop-cock S_2 was closed and S_3 and S_1 opened. The manometer was read again when the pressure was constant. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Time.	Barometric pressure.	Manometer reading.	Pressure in A.
0 min.	68·205 cm.	0·668 cm.	68·873 cm.
5	68·205	5·780	73·985
20	68·205	5·821	74·026
1 hr.	68·285	6·312	74·597
6	68·365	6·257	74·622
10	68·200	6·422	74·622

Calculation of the result.—Pressure change due to the liberation of air = $(74·622 - 68·873) = 5·749$ cm.

Aqueous tension at 30° = 3·130

Excess pressure due to displaced air = 2·619

Volume of the bulb A, up to the capillary = 99·8 c.c.

Weight of the gel taken = 4·443 g.

Hence, the vol. of air (at 30° and 76 cm. pressure) per g. of the gel

$$= \frac{99·8 \times 2·69}{4·443 \times 76}$$

$$= 0·474 \text{ c.c.}$$

A duplicate experiment gave a value = 0·768 c.c. per g.

The average value = 0·771 c.c./g.

The volume of water adsorbed by 1 g. of the gel at saturated vapour pressure = 0·337 ,,

If this volume is taken as the total internal gel volume, the average pressure of the air inside the gel capillaries

$$= \frac{0·771}{0·337} = 2·289 \text{ atmos.}$$

Air liberated when water wets silica gel which is immersed under an organic liquid.—During the displacement of an adsorbed organic liquid by water a certain volume of air is liberated. The volume of

air thus set free was measured using the apparatus shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2.

The bulb A, was completely filled with the organic liquid up to the stop-cock S_4 . Immersed in this was a weighed quantity of the gel. The space enclosed by the stop-cocks S_1 , S_2 and S_3 was filled with water through S_2 . As in the previous experiment the apparatus was immersed in a water thermostat till the level of the liquid in the graduated tube P was constant for 30 minutes. On opening S_1 and S_3 , water gradually wetted the gel. After about two minutes bubbles of gas appeared round the gel particles and gradually collected at C, causing a corresponding rise in the tube P. The final reading was taken after 15 hours there being no appreciable rise after 10 hours. The results are given in Table II. The air liberated was analysed by standard methods of gas analysis

using Ambler's apparatus (*Analyst*, 1929, 54, 517) and found to contain 16.2% oxygen and 83.8% of nitrogen.

TABLE II.

Liquid displaced by water.	Vol. change during displacement.	Air liberated of gel.	Average pressure of air in corresponding capillary space.
1	2	3	4
Benzene	0.0085 c.c./g.	0.0937 c.c./g.	11.0 atmos.
Nitrobenzene	0.0107	0.1184	11.0
Carbon tetrachloride	0.0200	0.1677	8.5

In this table, column 1 gives the particular organic liquid in which the gel was immersed before wetting with water. In column 2 the volume decreases on displacement of the organic liquid by water (as described in Part III, p. 332) is given. Column 3 represents the volume of air liberated during the displacement of the liquid (in which the gel

was merely immersed without previous evacuation) by water. The result of column 4 is obtained by dividing the volume of air liberated by the volume change.

DISCUSSION.

In the calculation of the results in column 4, Table II, it has been assumed that when the gel is immersed in a liquid like benzene, the space which is not accessible to it (but accessible to water) in the gel is filled up with air under pressure. Another assumption made is that the liquid occupies all the space available for it in the gel, whether the gel is evacuated or not before the introduction of the liquid. Similar results were obtained by Patrick and Opdycke (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 601), who state that the amount of sulphur dioxide taken up by silica gel is the same, whether the experiment is done by the static or the dynamic method. On these assumptions it has been shown that when the gel is immersed in a liquid, the air which is present in the gel space (not accessible to liquid) will be at a high pressure, the pressure depending upon the particular liquid used. Thus in the case of benzene the pressure is 11 atmos. while it is 8 atmos. in the case of carbon tetrachloride.

SUMMARY.

1. The volume of air liberated from silica gel (when water wets it) has been measured and it has been shown that the air has an average pressure of two atmos. in the gel space.

2. It has been shown that the average pressure of air inside the gel space when it adsorbs a liquid will be about 10 atmos depending upon the particular liquid.

3. It is suggested that the air in the finest capillaries is held with great tenacity and can only be displaced by water.